

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CONCEPTUALIZATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENGLISH COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF PHILOLOGY STUDENTS THROUGH THE DISCURSIVE APPROACH TO THE LITERARY TEXT

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Abstract

The article describes the Pedagogical Model of the development of the English communicative competence of Philology students through the discursive approach to the literary text that was elaborated, implemented and validated in the process of studying English. It was realized from the perspective of the role of the discursive approach in the communicative paradigm in the English language, based on student-centered learning, major concepts of glottodactics, socioconstructivist learning theories.

Keywords: literary text, model, communicative competence, discursive approach, context.

The Pedagogic Model is made up of elements which represent systems that ensure its integrity, that distinguish action, cognitive, attitudinal and procedural structures which are in reciprocal relation. The Pedagogical Model of the development of the English communicative competence of Philology students through the discursive approach to the literary text represents a methodological construct that stimulates the didactic approach to the development of the given competence, taking into account the standards of professional communicative competence in the English language, the purpose, the objectives of the didactic approach to the development of the communicative competence, the

pedagogical principles and conditions (linguistic, psycholinguistic and methodological) of the development of the communicative competence.

The central point of the Pedagogical Model is the contents of the discursive approach to the literary text, which provides advantages for the development of the communicative competence in English at the level of knowledge, application and integration (Picture 1).

The evaluation criteria of the elaborated Pedagogical Model are established on the basis of the Professional Training Standards of Philology students which must be achieved at the end of the first cycle (bachelor's degree) of the process of studying English as a foreign language (Table 1).

Picture 1. Pedagogical Model of the development of the English communicative competence through the discursive approach to the literary text

In the Republic of Moldova, the National Framework of Higher Education Qualifications is the domestic document that describes the system of teachers' professional competences [1].

Table 1.

General competences for the specialists in modern languages and classical languages (according to the National Qualifications Framework: Higher Education)

Specific skills for the specialists in modern languages and classical languages	Generalization of linguistic, literary and civilizational knowledge.
	Identification of the theoretical bases of linguistics, literary science and the existing problems in these fields.
	Identification of linguistic units, their relationship, the processes that affect them and the literary, civilizational and intercultural processes.
	Interpretation of linguistic and literary theories.
	Application of the studied linguistic and literary theories to the research of a particular phenomenon.
	Ability to select linguistic data, to constitute a corpus, to interpret and use the information from them for argumentation.
	Use of linguistic and literary analysis methods that are appropriate to the type of research.
	Formulation of the legalities of the functioning of the linguistic, literary and cultural mechanisms.
	Analysis of the linguistic and literary phenomena from diachronic, synchronic, social perspectives.
	Identification of different types and sources of meanings according to languages.
	Use of specialized language depending on the target audience.
	Use of appropriate means in the re- and production of a text.

Researchers T. Callo, A. Paniş, V. Andriţchi encourage the idea that, within the development of the competence, several certain stages must be gradually completed, based on the algorithm *Competence = Fundamental knowledge + Functional knowledge + Behavior/Attitude* [2, p. 79].

In this regard, the purpose of the Pedagogical Model is formulated and it consists in the development of the English communicative competence of Philology students through the discursive approach to the literary text, specified both at the discursive and sociocultural level, developed in order to optimize the process of the professional communication in English, which will favor the creation of the English discursive culture of Philology students.

At the *knowledge level*, the development of the communicative competence process reflects several specific objectives: establishing the functioning of various utterances in terms of language, rhetorical and linguistic mechanisms; determining, within the text structure, the lexical-grammatical degree and its contribution to the production of discourse; identifying certain characteristics of social and regional varieties, as well as the application of more distinctive characteristics in the formation of a certain speech; establishing text structures with connotative content, cultural, historical and social references; distinguishing the categories of linguistic means by using the appropriate connectors to indicate points of view, statements or arguments.

At the *application level*, the achievement of the specific objectives of the development of the English communicative competence imply the ability of an easy transition between registers, emphasizing the features of the used one; the narration, through the use of spatial, temporal and logical connectors, of a coherent and long story; the presentation of a rather complicated narrative, which reflects secondary themes, but also more developed themes, which suppose an appropriate conclusion; the correct and precise presentation of ideas, through appropriately structured information, in more

complex statements; the formulation of a structured, fluent and clear text, demonstrating the controlled use of appropriate examples, arguments and the linguistic means of articulation and structure; accurate reception of statements and opinions that note similarity, trust or distrust, certainty or doubt; produce complex, long, cohesive and well-organized texts using organizational charts as well as various linking/articulating words; arguments by paraphrasing and reformulating certain textual structures.

At the *integration level*, the language should be adapted to the change of the discourse topic and the communicative situation, in order to demonstrate the ability to initiate, continue and complete the message; producing/developing a coherent, long text, through examples and arguments, through fluency and spontaneity; expressing an intention and attitude for intervening in the discussion using certain linguistic units; the precise apprehension of the means of giving feedback to questions and of understanding the storyteller's intention, of interpreting the speakers' signs.

The Pedagogical Model involves textual and contextual analysis, but also the analysis of discursive strategies used in various communicative situations.

Given the fact that speech is a social practice, the discursive approach focuses on the sociocultural and discursive aspects of communication, the ways people speak using discursive strategies and resources; the communicative situation that places the receiver outside the text; the study of the phenomena from the reality determined by the context (the conditions of the text production), through the interaction of sender - message/code - receiver.

In the analysis of the communicative situation, considerable attention is paid to aspects such as sociocultural awareness, textual coherence and cohesion, precision and order of thought, inference of meaning by readers, thematic development, adaptation of the reader to the context, relationship between the author and the

reader, and not only the relationship that exists between one sentence or another [3].

The implementation of the Pedagogical Model aims at the development of communicative skills in English based on the requirements of social reality, conditioned by the presence of certain social and psycho-pedagogical factors such as:

- **psycho-pedagogical factor** - involves students' training taking into account the need for discursive skills in didactic communication and the entire professional activity;

- **social factor** – in the context of the complexity of today's society, the competences system becomes an innovative type of the purposes on which higher education focuses, and the emphasis shifts to the pragmatic dimension of the English language;

- **psycholinguistic factor** – communication of information in two ways (content and expression), mutual understanding, materialization of the social role of language, adaptation to sociocultural circumstances, etc.;

- **psychological factor** – motivation, attitudes, expression of thoughts, emotions, interactive abilities, communication.

The methodological system is guided by general and particular/specific didactic principles. These principles are common to all disciplines of study and represent certain norms that order or regulate each level of the development of the English communicative competence of Philology students.

The examination of the researches in the field allowed the establishment of certain specific methodical principles that substantiated the Methodology of the discursive approach to the literary text.

In this context, we state that the didactic process of developing the English communicative competence in English through the discursive approach to the literary text must be governed by the following specific principles of the text interpretation. These principles are regulated by certain psychopedagogical conditions and constitute an important condition for the development of the English discursive communicative competence (Table 2).

Formative educational activities, generated by the principles mentioned, offer possibilities for the development of certain specific capacities of Philology students. A capacity, in this sense, is the discursive one, as an element of the pragmatic-discursive competence.

Table 2.

Principles and psychopedagogical conditions that substantiate the process of literary text analysis

<i>Pragmasentic principle</i>	<i>Dialogical principle</i>	<i>Intertextuality principle</i>	<i>Principle of cooperative text interpretation</i>	<i>Principle of intercultural communication</i>
Psychopedagogical conditions				
-involvement of the sociocultural conditions in the reception of the text meaning; -establishment of the text message in the communicative situation; -presence of the factors of text production in the text reception.	-interactivity between the text and its context; -interrelation between the dialog and the discursive perspective; -interactive feature of the student-centered training process.	-text mediation; -text polyphony; -choice of a learning situation and its placement in a real learning context.	-intercultural dimension of the text; -participants' cooperation to the text analysis; -enhancement of the motivation in the process of the text interpretation.	-perception of cultural norms and values of the society where the language is spoken; -distinction of the cultural context.

The skills formation and development is a process organized in three steps:

- **The stage of preparing to learn:** the teacher provides students with the information they need to prepare for the task (declarative knowledge: WHAT?) and for the purpose of using this task (conditional knowledge: WHY?).

- **Accomplishing the task:** the teaching staff formulates the task and guides the student on how to accomplish it and how to process the received information (procedural knowledge: HOW?).

- **Transfer of training to other circumstances:** the teacher proposes different learning situations in which the student reinvents what has been learned (conditional knowledge: WHEN?)

Respecting these stages that contribute to the development of any competence, we exploited the task-based learning Model, recommended by the researcher

J. Willis which was favored as a milestone in the development of our Pedagogical Model.

The complementary Volume of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages published in 2018 gives particular importance to the valorization of the action paradigm by achieving task-based learning and authentic situations in order to satisfy the students' communicative needs [4].

The Pedagogical Model of the development of the English communicative competence of Philology students through the discursive approach to the literary text was developed and placed in the communication paradigm but with the achievement of authentic tasks, used and integrated separately in the process of developing the English communicative competence of Philology students.

The communicative competence that is a set of knowledge, abilities, attitudes and values, in the pro-

cess of its development through the discursive approach to the literary text, goes through several phases, uncodified and relative, being in permanent evolution and cyclical relationship.

In this regard, we took up the stages/phases of task-based learning proposed by J. Willis [ibidem].

The didactic process of the discursive approach is carried out by observing the organizational stages of the work process (pre-task, task cycle, post-task), through educational strategies (methods, learning techniques, forms of organization and learning means).

Each stage included a set of didactic situations achieved through cognitive, integrative and evaluative tasks.

In the first stage, *Pre-Task*, teachers, together with the students, examine the topic. They preview the tasks ahead and note the most important vocabulary items.

Pre-assignment activities are a catalyst for reading and discussion aimed at motivating the students through introductory activities. An important contribution to the organization of an additional dialogue between the students and teachers, as well as to the achievement of a suitable result belongs to referential questions [5].

During the completion of the task, the students get involved in various activities that make their reception of textual messages more efficient, by obtaining general information in order to establish the subject, the theme, the context and by practicing certain linguistic structures existing in the text. Through certain schemes such as mind maps, prediction, preview, the students predict the text message by connecting it to their previous experiences. By means of the mind map, information can be organized, structured, learned, arranged and memorized efficiently [6].

At the *Task-cycle* stage, the students are familiarized with the textual elements of content and structure. At this stage, the literary meaning reflected in the text is received and mediated through various activities. The discursive analysis of the literary text includes categories of structural levels of language, such as:

- use of vocabulary and terminology;
- use of specific grammatical forms (such as nominalizations, position markers, amplifiers, euphemisms, rhetorical questions, politeness formulas, impoliteness, temporal and modal deixism, stylistic figures, metaphor, anaphora) etc.;
- description of prototypical textual sequences (description, explanation, narration, argumentation);
- use of textual markers, researching multimodal elements or subjectivity and evaluation markers.

In this context, the students can acquire a wide range of pragmatic and sociocultural skills; skills to receive and produce written and oral messages; a wide range of skills developed through analysis, cooperation, debate, discussion, action, observation, communication and thinking. Therefore, the tasks are integrative, applicative, specific to real situations.

Given the particularities of discourse, namely situationality, in the process of the discursive approach to the literary text, there should be exploited the methodological potentiality of the communicative situation. It

is realized through a wide spectrum of discursive practices and tasks, which reflect the transition from analytical thinking to gradually distributed discursive actions (from simple to compound).

During the experiment there were applied tasks based on contextualized problem solving, investigation and discovery of meaningful solutions, interactive and cooperative learning through building dialogues. The task goes through 3 phases: first of all, the task is set and presented to the learners, then they plan and design its realization. The students reflect on their learning process and present their results.

The stage that follows the task, called *Post-Task*, involves certain didactic activities aimed at determining and evaluating various aspects of the textual content, the value of cultural aspects and their influence in the text interpretation. This stage is equivalent to cognitive mediation, where students are involved in various interactive activities carried out by means of didactic strategies and communicative application tasks, through problematization, cooperation and discovery tasks. Learning through discovery begins with a question-problem.

The use of discursive tasks at this stage stimulates the students' ability to rationalize, negotiate, accept, argue, paraphrase, refuse, impose opinions, causing various discussions with the help of didactic strategies to synthesize their own experiences with those in the text, problem-solving activities, realization of mini-projects, debates, case studies, mind maps or role-playing [6].

The realization of the Pedagogical Model involves certain strategic components that reflect the *Technology of the development of discursive capacity* as an element of the English communicative competence of Philology students through the discursive approach to the literary text which is the structural set of didactic strategies applied through a strong reciprocal relationship with the instructional forms, the contents, the outcomes, but also a certain higher form of didactic normativity, which favors the achievement and regulation of the teaching-learning process.

The development of the English communicative competence of Philology students focused on the use of the *Pedagogical Technology* of the correlation of methods, techniques, procedures and strategies, involving a set of operations within the framework of teaching-learning-evaluation. In other words, the Pedagogical Technology represents all the activities designated to achieve the goal and obtain a result.

The role of the *discursive strategy* included in the Pedagogical Technology is significant, as it presents a multitude of methods, procedures or processes and operations directed towards the realization of certain objectives.

Thus, by *discursive strategy* we mean the way the teacher designs in creating an interaction process, by examining a set of logical and linguistic procedures (the combination of statements in discursive sequences, reasoning discursive forms, types of arguments, methods of description and explanation, stylistic-persuasive procedures) in order to develop the student's discursive capacity as an element of pragmatic-discursive competence.

Discursive tasks performed through various learning processes, methods and situations have gained significant value in the development of the English communicative competence.

Within the targeted discursive strategy, there was functionally taken into account a certain action model. This is motivated by the fact that all the processes occurring within the designed activity cannot be carried out through a single activity.

Among the essential components of the didactic technology and strategy there are listed the *methods* that reflect a system of appropriate ways aimed at favoring the realization of the process, ensuring its completion. They unite the act of teaching and learning into a whole, influencing each other, depending on the intended objective [7].

Thus, the methods used are: role play, project method, problem-solving, case study, dialogue, etc. The formative values of these interactive methods are determined by the teacher's strategy, the information support and the students' abilities.

The *didactic technique* is used, in a general sense, as a method representing another component of the operation strategy [8. p. 307]. In developing the Pedagogical Model, we relied on the concept of *technique* proposed by I. Bontaş, and considered as the combination of certain procedures and practical solutions, along with certain means, with a view to effectively carry out some didactic activities. [9, p. 160].

During the formative experiment, there were implemented the following techniques: Agenda with double notes, Cube method, Multi-process questioning, Verbal picture, 5 Whys?, Webquest, Gallery tour, Mind map, Clustering, Venn diagram, T-chart, etc.

Through the Pedagogical Model of the development of the English communicative competence of Philology students through the discursive approach to the literary text, there were created certain learning situations that make students interact, discover other realities, research, mediate social-cultural situations that can generate tensions, conflicts, disagreement and misunderstandings.

The right choice of learning situations requires the development of a methodology for exploiting collaborative and learning through discovery, task-based and student-centred learning.

We reiterate that the methodology of the discursive approach to the literary text provides tasks that ensure the training value of authentic material practiced in learning experiences.

In task-based learning, the students are given problems that require solving. This type of learning consists in researching certain authentic situations by means of exact, concrete actions. Students must individually identify at least one solution to solve the learning task, the actions must be planned and applied, then the reflection of the learning process must be carried out and finally the results must be demonstrated. In any new situation occurring in the learning process, it is important for the student to determine his learning needs. In this way, through analysis, cooperation, experiment, discussion, thinking, debate, action, observation, communication, etc., students develop their knowledge,

skills, attitudes, a wide range of speech production and reception skills [10].

The discursive approach to the literary text is also achieved through another important strategy – learning through discovery. Currently, the educational process emphasizes how you know, not quantity, i.e. what and how much you know. It is important how you search and process ideas in your own style, how you mediate a knowledge conflict between cognitive experiences [11].

From the category of learning strategies through discovery and collaboration, we used the following techniques in the study process: Agenda with double notes, Cube Method, Star Explosion, 5 Whys?, Cinqvain, Verbal Picture, Dialogue, Clustering, Mini-Project, Gallery Tour, Mind Map, Group Lotus, Spider Technique etc.

Learning through discovery gives priority not only to the result of the cognitive process, but specifically to the ways of achieving this result. The teaching staff guides the students in their exploratory path, which is carried out through the analysis of literary texts, the conclusion of the facts, events and processes notified [12].

The condition for the development of this type of learning is the problematizing environment, the method constituting a continuation of the problematization and the debate considered as its outcome.

Another type of learning is focused on solving problems that contribute to the development of knowledge and capabilities through extensive tasks, involving inquiry and authentic demonstrations of learning through performance and outcomes.

From the category of learning strategies through problematization, we used the following techniques in the process of literary text interpretation: Case study, Role-play, Simulation, Poster, Spider Technique, Project etc.

Discursive tasks are carried out by means of didactic strategies and types of learning that require the student to valorize his skills in using the socio-cultural and discursive aspects of the English language, the manifestation of coherence and cohesion in structuring the statement, the development of fluency, correctness, precision and logical speech, thinking and creativity.

The outcomes are the most important elements of the Pedagogical Model. The National Qualifications Framework presents them as an expression of the learning product. The functionality of academic acquisitions determines the rendering of learning outcomes in terms of competences. [13, p. 7].

The outcomes formulated within the Pedagogical Model aim at the mastery of the English communicative competence. This competence represents the dynamic relationship between knowledge, abilities and attitudes, which describe the purpose of the research: the development of English communicative competence of Philology students (*the development of the discursive capacity as an element of the communicative competence*).

Thus, the competence is not limited to the complete characteristic of the professional's personal and professional qualities, which reveal the degree of

knowledge and skills, sufficient to achieve the objective specific to the field of activity, but it reflects as well the persistent integrity of the student who intends to reach the goal of his professional activity.

The outcome of the literary text analysis process consists in the student's ability to correlate the means of discourse (convictions, explanations, arguments, descriptions, agreements, refusals, demonstrations) in order to effectively receive the image created in an authentic context, from the real world.

Thus, the discursive approach considers the literary text as a source that favors stimulating activities with a view to acquire language structures. The varied styles and registers that literary texts contain, encourage discussions focused on stimulating and motivating themes, they allow more interpretations that generate interaction within the English classroom. The discursive approach to the literary text also reflects the enunciation of competent judgments following the examination of linguistic textual features, in order to achieve the perception of how meanings are conveyed. As a result of the discursive approach to the literary text, there are developed such values and attitudes as: *motivation, correctness, trust, fluency, coherence, interaction, tolerance and interest*.

In this regard, we conclude that the effectiveness of the development of English communicative competence aims at the establishment of methodological and theoretical benchmarks for the elaboration of the Pedagogical Model of the development of the English communicative competence of Philology students through the discursive approach to the literary text.

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